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<p>Global evaluation schema</p> <p>Assess your research using your region's evaluation framework with over 13 localized classifications used in national research assessment exercises.</p>	<p>Multiple ways to view data</p> <p>Quickly assess the research landscape on any topic to identify star researchers, centers of excellence, and major funders- worldwide or in your region of choice.</p>	<p>Customized reporting</p> <p>Gain confidence in your internal assessments with reporting that reflects your departmental structure in the My Organization module.</p>
<p>Trend analysis</p> <p>Identify emerging trends or perform retrospective analyses with over 40 years of content from the world's leading research publications.</p>	<p>Institutional profiles</p> <p>Gain a multidimensional and unbiased comparison of all aspects of your performance regardless of your institution's mission, size, geographical location, or subject mix.</p>	<p>Responsible metrics</p> <p>Be a leader in responsible research evaluation using a resource developed according to best practices outlined by the unbiased experts at the Institute for Scientific Information.</p>

Benchmarking & Analytics Indicators

Comparison 'like with like'

Productivity And Impact	Normalization	Top Performance	Scientific Collaborations	JIF Documents
Web of Science Documents	Category Normalized Citation Impact	% Documents in Top 1%	% Industry Collaborations	Documents in JIF Journals
Times Cited	Category Expected Citations	% Documents in Top 10%	% International Collaborations	Documents in Q1 Journals
Citation Impact	Journal Normalized Citation Impact	Average percentile	Collaborations with Organizations	Documents in Q2 Journals
% of documents cited	Journal Expected Citations	Highly Cited Papers	Collaborations with Countries	Documents in Q3 Journals
H Index		Hot Papers	Collaborations with Authors	Documents in Q4 Journals

What's New ▾

System Requirements

Registration and Sign-in

Analyze ▴

Working with the Explorer ▾

Researchers

Organizations

Regions

Research Areas

Publication Sources

Funding Agencies

Report ▾

Organize ▾

Custom Datasets

My Organization Module

Explore InCites Data

The InCites Explorer is a tool for analyzing the People, Organizations, Regions, Research Areas, Journals, Books, Conference Proceedings and Funding Agencies included in the InCites dataset and is powered by the Web of Science Core Collection indexes. Data in InCites is updated monthly (usually towards the end of the month) and is based on the Web of Science data extracted towards the end of the previous month. The data update schedule for InCites is available here.

After registration and sign-in, you will be directed the main landing page within the application where InCites data is organized in to three main boxes as shown below.

The header bar at the top serves as a quick access toolbar where you can jump of each individual entity or reports or organize your data into folders and dashboards.

The question mark at the bottom right is called as the "Resource Center" and allows you to view Product Announcements, Guides and walk-throughs.

New landing page
quickly start analyses, access reports, or organize your projects.

Quick access
remains available - in the same location - for expert users who know precisely where they want to go.

Analyze
access the ready-to-use starter analyses.

Report
create new reports, access system reports.

Organize
manage your dashboards, reports, and datasets.

h5-index:376 h5-median:552

#1 Life Sciences & Earth Sciences

#1 Life Sciences & Earth Sciences (general)

Title / Author	Cited by	Year
Deep learning. Y LeCun, Y Bengio, G Hinton Nature 521 (7553), 436	27375	2015
Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning. V Mnih, K Kavukcuoglu, D Silver, AA Rusu, J Veness, MG Bellemare, ... Nature 518 (7540), 529-533	10394	2015
Mastering the game of Go with deep neural networks and tree search. D Silver, A Huang, CJ Maddison, A Guez, L Sifre, G van den Driessche, ... Nature 529 (7587), 484	7698	2016
Analysis of protein-coding genetic variation in 60,706 humans. M Lek, KJ Karczewski, EV Minikel, KE Samocha, E Banks, T Fennell, ... Nature 536 (7616), 285-291	6387	2016
A global reference for human genetic variation. A Auton, LD Brooks, RM Durbin, EP Garrison, HM Kang, JO Korbel, ... Nature 526 (7571), 68-74	6044	2015
Dermatologist-level classification of skin cancer with deep neural networks. A Esteva, B Kuprel, RA Novoa, J Ko, SM Swetter, HM Blau, S Thrun Nature 542 (7639), 115-118		

top publications

Categories ▾

English ▾

Publication	h5-index	h5-median
1. Nature	376	552
2. The New England Journal of Medicine	365	639
3. Science	356	526
4. The Lancet	301	493
5. IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition	299	509
6. Advanced Materials	273	369
7. Nature Communications	273	366
8. Cell	269	417
9. Chemical Reviews	267	438
10. Chemical Society reviews	240	368
11. Journal of the American Chemical Society	236	324
12. Angewandte Chemie	229	316
13. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences	228	299
14. JAMA	220	337
15. Nucleic Acids Research	219	475
16. Physical Review Letters	209	288
17. International Conference on Learning Representations	203	359
18. Journal of Clinical Oncology	202	300
19. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	201	263

Journal Selector

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Sort results by title, impact factor or frequency.

Filter results by field of study, impact factor range, SCI-E index and Open Access options.

Make a Decision

Access detailed information about the journal to make a more informed decision.

28 000 revues

search MIAR

 Search Title Search

Title index

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z

Other index ---

40 000 revues

- 44197 journals
- 117 databases
- 6 evaluation repertories

News

- Update to MIAR2018 Live 13-02-2018
- Update to MIAR 2017 Live 17-03-2017
- Changes in the ICDS 2016 calculation 03-05-2016

MIAR collects data for the identification and the analysis of scientific journals. If you enter an ISSN in the search box, the system will check in which **databases**, those referred to in the matrix, the journal is indexed. That is regardless of whether the journal is included with a full description in MIAR or not. The system will also calculates an index called the **ICDS**. If the journal is not included in MIAR, the value of the Survival Index will not be given.

MIAR is a COLLABORATIVE tool. **Publishers, authors and readers can suggest new journals**, report errors, supply news, or share data on social networks. **Publishers can also include value-added information about their journals** provided that it can be validated against a public source in the Internet.

MIAR has an INTEGRATED approach. Apart from showing the visibility of journals in abstracting and indexing databases, MIAR also provides information about journals from other evaluation tools, such

Tweets por @Miar_UB

MIAR retwitteó

Lluís Anglada @lluissanglada

Données de la recherche

Données de la recherche

Les données de la recherche sont définies comme des enregistrements factuels (chiffres, textes, images et sons), qui sont utilisés comme sources principales pour la recherche scientifique et sont généralement reconnus par la communauté scientifique comme nécessaires pour valider les résultats de la recherche»

(OCDE, [*Principes et lignes directrices pour l'accès aux données de la recherche financée sur fonds publics*](#), 2007)

chemistry

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 ... 13 Next

Found 311 results

Imperial College High Performance Computing Service Data Repository

Subjects: Humanities and Social Sciences Organic Molecular Chemistry Inorganic Molecular Chemistry Polymer Research Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry Analytical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry) Physical and Theoretical Chemistry Chemical Solid State and Surface Research Natural Sciences Chemistry Molecular Chemistry Polymer Materials Experimental and Theoretical Physics of Polymers Preparatory and Physical Chemistry of Polymers Food Chemistry Biological and Biomimetic Chemistry Analytical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry) General Theoretical Chemistry Physical Chemistry of Molecules, Interfaces and Liquids - Spectroscopy, Kinetics Theory and Modelling Physical Chemistry of Solids and Surfaces, Material Characterisation Solid State and Surface Chemistry, Material Synthesis

Content type(s): Structured text

Country: United Kingdom

A lightweight digital repository for data based on the concepts of collections of filesets. Both the collection and the fileset are assigned a DOI by the DataCite organisation which can be quoted in articles

ioChem-BD

Subjects: Natural Sciences Polymer Research Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry Analytical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry) Physical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry) General Theoretical Chemistry Physical Chemistry of Molecules, Interfaces and Liquids - Spectroscopy, Kinetics Physical and Theoretical Chemistry Physical Chemistry of Solids and Surfaces, Material Characterisation Solid State and Surface Chemistry, Material Synthesis Chemical Solid State and Surface Research Organic Molecular Chemistry Inorganic Molecular Chemistry Molecular Chemistry Chemistry

Content type(s): Plain text Images Structured text Scientific and statistical data formats

Country: Spain

ioChem-BD is a Digital Repository to manage Computational Chemistry and Material Science digital assets. The platform follows the philosophy of Crystallographic databases, the principles and needs of open access, and solves reproducibility and traceability issues.

The Canadian National Atmospheric Chemistry Database
The Canadian National Atmospheric Chemistry Database and Analysis System

Coronavirus Disease Research Community - COVID-19

Recent uploads

Search Coronavirus Disease Research Community - COVID-19

July 4, 2020 (20200720) Outdated Open Access

India Non Virus Deaths During lockdown
Aman, Kanika Sharma, Krishna R, Tejesh GN

This is a public database of reported deaths that have happened as a result of the lockdown. These include deaths due to starvation and financial distress, exhaustion, accidents during migration, lack or denial of medical care, suicides, police brutality, crimes, and alcohol-withdrawal. We also have

Uploaded on March 23, 2021

1 more version(s) exist for this record

March 23, 2021 (4) Other Open Access

Living Document I: Belgian mental health (care) data repository update 3
Van Hooft, Elke, De Laet, Hannah, Résoibols, Maxime, Gérard, Sylvie, Dekeyser, Sarah, Loix, Ellen, Phillips, Evelien, Shnoeck, Sylvia, Maratovska Saffulina, Zamira, Luminet, Olivier, Van den Cruyce, Niele

Covid-19 has had a big impact on many aspects of our life, including mental health. Since the start of the pandemic, a whole body of Belgian research has been performed on the relation between covid-19 and mental health (care). The mental health & covid-19 working group of the superior health co

Uploaded on March 23, 2021

3 more version(s) exist for this record

March 23, 2021 (1) Journal article Open Access

FOR A LIMITED PERIOD OF TIME: IMPLEMENTING EMERGENCY REMOTE TEACHING IN

GIGADB DATASETS

GigADB contains 2035 discoverable, trackable, and citable datasets that have been assigned DOIs and are available for public download and use.

e.g. Chicken, brain etc...

Dataset types + more RSS

- Genomic (1250)
- Software (294)
- Transcriptomic (209)
- Imaging (1188)
- Neuroscience (39)
- Epigenomic (37)
- Metagenomic (64)
- Genome mapping (17)
- Workflow (71)
- Proteomic (26)
- Metabarcoding (8)
- Metadata (14)

New dataset added on 2021-03-17: [10.5524/1100879](#)
Supporting data for "BiSulfite Bolt: A Bisulfite Sequencing Analysis Platform"

New dataset added on 2021-03-14: [10.5524/1100874](#)
Supporting data for "Chromosome-level genome assembly of the hard-shelled mussel *Mytilus coruscus*, a widely distributed species from the temperate areas of East Asia"

New dataset added on 2021-03-12: [10.5524/1100881](#)

Core Certified Repositories

Applications are made public only once certification of a data repository has been approved by the CoreTrustSeal Board. Certification is a Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements named in the link to the public application (e.g., 2017–2019). The CoreTrustSeal for Data Repository from the certification date listed within the public application.

all none

- WDS Certified Repositories [42]
- DSA Certified Repositories [17]
- CTS Certified Repositories [106]

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Marker ID

International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
<https://ices.dk/>
CoreTrustSeal certification 2020-2022

H. C. Andersens Boulevard 44-46, 1553 V, Copenhagen, Denmark

UK Polar Data Centre

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mcSCRB-seq protocol

Molecular Biology

Aleksandar Janjic, LMU München

Scientific runnable step-by-step protocols that can be shared, run, and published.

Spectrophotometry method

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Du Xiaohua

Spectrophotometry is a technique that is used to measure the concentration of solutes in a solution.

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A podcast that puts a spotlight on the painstaking and time-consuming labor of method development.

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China Earthquake Administration

Methods for earth science or geoscience which includes all fields of natural science related to the planet Earth.

Portail des Données médicales

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- [Catalogue des variations génétiques humaines](#)
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- [Base de données de séquences génétiques](#)
- [Portail des données biomédicales](#)

Plus de visibilité

- ✓ Inexactitude des affiliations (variations des formes d'écriture, adresse personnelles et non institutionnelle).

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UCH Maroc Ibn Rochd UHC	Pubmed:
Quartier des hôpitaux Casablanca Résidence Walili	WOS:

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Abada R.
Abada R.-A.-L.
Abada R.L.

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Alharrar R.
Al-Harrar R.

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Benghanem M.
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